

SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL GENDER ACTIVITY OF FEMALE SINGERS OF THE FERGANA VALLEY.

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Abstract. *The article describes the socio-pedagogical gender activities of female singers in folk dances organized in Uzbekistan.*

Key words: *gender, Farhod HPP, hydroelectric power plant, branch, modernization, folk art, construction, "People's artist", "People's hofizi", labor force.*

СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ ГЕНДЕРНАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ ПЕВИЦ ФЕРГАНСКОЙ ДОЛИНЫ.

Аннотация. *В статье описывается социально-педагогическая гендерная деятельность певиц в народных танцах, организованных в Узбекистане.*

Ключевые слова: *гендер, Фарходская ГЭС, гидроэлектростанция, отрасль, модернизация, народное творчество, строительство, «Народный артист», «Народный хофизи», рабочая сила.*

“The foundation for a new renaissance - the Third Renaissance - is being built in Uzbekistan”¹.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev.

People's activation is a strategy of involving them in achieving change, increasing public power and calling for action, so activism allows people to influence and change the issues that are the focus of the decision-making process.

Farhod HPP, one of the great constructions of the 20th century, which made a big difference in improving the standard of living of the peoples of Central Asia, is a hydroelectric power station located in the middle reaches of the Syr Darya, in the Farhod hydroelectric station. It became significant. The decision on the construction of the hydroelectric power plant was made in 1942. On May 18, 1943, the construction of the hydroelectric power plant was accepted.

On February 10, it was started as a public construction - by road. Farhod HPP, one of the great constructions of the 20th century, which made a big difference in the improvement of the

¹ President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev.

living standards of the people of Central Asia - the hydroelectric power station located in the middle stream of the Syr Darya, in the Farhod hydroelectric station, gained its importance in the construction of the subsidiary of the state joint-stock company "Uzbek Energy". The decision on the construction of the hydroelectric power plant was made in 1942. On May 18, 1943, the construction of the hydroelectric power plant was accepted. On February 10, it was started as a public construction - by road.

Power is transmitted at a voltage of 110, 35.6 kV. In 2003, it was connected to the Central Asian unified energy system ("Energy" unified dispatching center). 562 mln. Kilowatt hours of electricity produced. No. 2947 of the President of May 2, 2017 "On the program of measures for the further development of hydropower in 2017-2021" and No. 827 of the Cabinet of Ministers of October 18, 2018 "On the modernization of the Farhod" hydropower station Based on the decisions of the number, modernization and re-technical equipment of this HPP was carried out People of labor made prosperous Farhad steppe with flowers, 1948 The 1st hydrounit was commissioned in 1949. 4 hydro aggregate stations with a total capacity of 126 MW, installed in June, began to work at full capacity, and were accepted for industrial use in 1951. Syrdarya region cities and districts, as well as large enterprises such as "Bekobodcement" and "Uzbekistan Metallurgical Combine" have started to be supplied with electricity. Power is transmitted at a voltage of 110, 35.6 kV. In 2003, it was connected to the Central Asian unified energy system ("Energy" unified dispatching center). 562 mln. Kilowatt hours of electricity produced. No. 2947 of the President of May 2, 2017 "On the program of measures for the further development of hydropower in 2017-2021" and No. 827 of the Cabinet of Ministers of October 18, 2018 "On the modernization of the Farhod" hydropower station Based on the decisions of the number, modernization and re-technical equipment of this HPP was carried out

People of labor made prosperous Farhad steppe with flowers,
Deserts have become deserts, no birds can fly anymore,
My insufferable enemy screams and makes a thousand spots on his chest,
Keep working tirelessly, friends.

In particular, the large Fergana canal, as one of the largest hydrotechnical structures built in the valley, caused huge transformational changes in the territory of Uzbekistan (283 km), Tajikistan (62 km) and Kyrgyzstan (13 km). Since ancient times, people have been engaged in land development by digging canals and ditches to subdue the water sources necessary for life.

Since the inhabitants of the country have been engaged in agriculture, they have always felt the need for water. The construction of the Big Fergana Canal satisfied the population's need for fertile land and made it possible to create fields, gardens and vineyards.

The Great Fergana Canal was completed in 45 days with the solidarity of our hardworking and selfless people in a very short period of time with the people's struggle that started on August 1, 1939. After that, the Great Fergana Canal was extended again in 1940 in the territory of Tajikistan. The water supply of 500,000 hectares of irrigated land in Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Tajikistan has improved, and the possibility of new land development has appeared.

180,000 people took part in the Great Fergana Canal Public Excavation, and 17.8 million m³ of soil was excavated along the 270 km long route (of which only 1.7 million m³ of soil was used by machinery). The canal was reconstructed in 1953-62, 1964 and 1967. The length was increased to 345 km, the water consumption was 180 m³/s, the fastest water consumption was 211 m³/s. The water supply of 500,000 irrigated lands in Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Tajikistan has improved, and the opportunity to develop new lands has appeared. More than 1,000 hydrotechnical structures (50 of them are large), including 9 dams, 258 water outlets with a maximum gross water intake of 162 m³/s, 7 spillways, and 8 aqueducts were built on the canal. 101 bridges were built to allow traffic to pass through the canal.

The Uzbek people united for a common goal at the Great Ferghana Canal and showed examples of true heroism. The service of representatives of all fields, including artists, who strived towards the goal in unity and harmony, was incomparable. During the construction of the canal, every evening there was a torch party of the canal diggers in the open field, and everyone showed their talent and art. Among them, people's artists of Uzbekistan Halima Nasirova, Mukarrama Turgunboeva, Fatima Borukhova, Tamarakhonim, Yusufjan Khenev, Zhorakhan Sultanov and brother Bukhor presented their art to our hardworking people.

“According to the recollections of the participants of the Great Fergana Canal, poets and musicians-singers worked tirelessly among the builders for forty-five days. It should be mentioned separately that the big song genre was performed with poems suitable for large structures and was liked by the connoisseurs. Contemporary poems by poets such as Habibiy, Sabir Abdulla, Chustiy, Kamtar are set to great hymn tunes, performed by singers such as Mamadbobo Satorov, Jorakhan Sultanov, Boltaboy Rajabov, Sherkozi Boykoziev, Hadyakhan Hamdamova, Zaynab Polvonova, Mehrikhon Abdullaveva. of diggers. received great applause.

In those years, many of our singers-composers won the sincere love of the people, and many of them were given the proud titles of “People's artist” and “People's memory”.

Good luck to those who are loyal to their country.

Good luck to those who are happy in this country, good luck to the successful growers.

Your enthusiasm is like a river, Your respect is like a world.

Shona's flowers are full of flowers, O successful growers.

You have shown your covenant, your agreement, you have promised, your buston.

May your gold mine flourish more and more, O successful growers.

These are the sons of the motherland, the Lion boys, and the girls are wrestlers.

They always sacrifice their lives for the people, O successful growers.

Among the hard-working and selfless, passionate female artists of the Fergana Valley are Mukarrama Azizova, Berta Davidova, Komuna Ismailova, Zaynab Polvonova, Lutfikhon Sarimsokova, Hadyakhan Hamdamova, Halima Nosirova, Fatima Borukhovalar, Farhod Hydroelectric Station, Big Fergana Channel, They served with their excellent performances and hard work in large public infrastructure constructions such as the Kosonsoy reservoir, the Northern Fergana canal, and the Logon canal.

In today's advanced age, the attitude towards women and the opportunities created for them are limitless. This, in turn, reflects the fact that it is based on national traditions and, at the same time, universal values. After all, the spiritual level of any nation is determined first of all by the spiritual level of the women of that country. The attitude towards women in our country has its historical roots. Our ancestors always encouraged us to value women, to respect them. It was not for nothing that our enlightened grandfathers said, "If a woman rises, humanity rises."

This ancient history is a witness to the bravery of hundreds of our honorable women like Tomaris, Saraymulkhanim, Nadirabegim, Gulbadanbegim, Uvaisi, Dilshad atin, Anbar atin, Zulfiya in the way of preserving the honor and dignity of the nation. The unique qualities characteristic of our mothers are embodied in the form of women of our time. After all, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. As Mirziyoev noted, "A country where women are honored becomes powerful." In the process of large-scale and rapid reforms taking place in new Uzbekistan, increasing the socio-political activity of women, ensuring their rights and interests, gender equality, protecting the family, motherhood and childhood, supporting creativity and initiatives, labor and the state policy to improve living conditions has reached a new level. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2018 "On measures to fundamentally improve activities in the field of supporting women and girls and strengthening the family institution", Decree No. PF-53 25 dated March 7, 2019 "Wife - the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to further strengthen guarantees of women's labor rights and support entrepreneurship, January 8, 2021 "Social support for women".

The adoption of decision No. 2 "On additional measures" is a clear expression of this. Today, as a result of our large-scale reforms, the creative processes of our women are getting stronger. Currently, women in our country are showing their talent and potential in all spheres of society.

Our women also have a significant contribution in the development of the fields of education, medicine, science, culture and sports. When we say a modern enlightened woman, we come to our eyes today's heroines who strive for progress faithfully to our national traditions, are initiators and organizers, and combine the status of femininity with research, leadership, and mentorship. The highest award of our country - "Hero of Uzbekistan", as well as "People's teacher", "People's poet", "People's artist" - are the majority of women.

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